

HOW EXTREME POVERTY RELATES TO LOW EDUCATIONAL PERFORMANCE IN SCHOOL LEARNING

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ABSTRACT

This work addresses the question of how extreme poverty is related to low educational performance in school learning. Its scientific relevance lies in the fact that it brings to the academic world a necessary discussion based on a human and political-social ideological bias and with broad scientific clarity. Its social relevance lies in being able to discuss, in a simple way, a problem that seems to be individual, but which takes on political proportions of the State, due to its direct and indirect impact on the social organization of the country. It is an essay, based on the author's participant observation, acting in public schools and in the literature on the subject. It is characterized as an interdisciplinary study, as it involves themes related to Biology, Economics, Sociology, Nutrition, Politics. Poverty, in its most aggravating state, leads to the process of malnutrition, malnutrition and hunger, which results in significant losses of nutrients essential to the formation of the synaptic structure, formation of neurons and other mechanisms that represent the basis of intellectual formation, because before being a cognitive procedure, learning goes through nutritional and health-based processes. The conclusions reached are that when combating extreme poverty, systematically, the problems related to low rates of educational-school learning tend to be minimized.

Keywords: Extreme poverty. Low educational-school performance. School learning.

INTRODUCTION

Thinking about the problem of education in Brazil is a situation that must be done with all the effort and with the help of different areas of scientific knowledge, in order to be able to

get closer to a more robust and equitable understanding of the problem of low levels of educational-academic performance that, generally, come from students from the poorest and, therefore, most vulnerable sections of the population.

It is not important here to develop a new form of stigma or social segregation based on a scientific essay that aims to show, in a dialectical way, what is the main cause of these children's low learning, when compared to the guiding models of curriculum and expected performance for each grade-year of the Brazilian educational system.

Brazilian education has always been at the mercy of ideologies that try to explain, with forceps, the problems that compose it and, therefore, instead of trying to solve the challenges posed, based on serious studies, using appropriate methodologies and of an empirical nature, dialoguing, in a dialectical way, with other scientific aspects, such assumptions end up validating hypotheses about *possible causes*, not paying attention to the deeper and real scope of the situation, in which cognitive disability does not represent *the problem in itself*; but, one symptom, among many others, remaining the *root cause*, placed on the margins of studies and academic-scientific discussions.

And with this myopic vision, curriculum ideologists, thinkers of solutions to pedagogical- educational problems, are always presenting new curriculum theories, psychopedagogical, pedagogical and psychological proposals, as if such ideas could solve the problems that directly affect a layer of the population, which despite all the effort to level the collective intellectuality at the bottom, are not capable of promoting the civil inclusion of these individuals. These arrangements are so charming that they end up with everyone not attacking the problem in its basic structure, conditioning this part of the population to neglect, *because all pedagogical alternatives of teaching and methodological strategies have been tried without any results*.

It turns out that the acquisition of school learning, which for Goñi (2019), represents the acquisition and consolidation of knowledge, is a direct consequence and does not cause [*direct and/or indirect*] influence on the student, which already implies that this condition depends on their psychophysical conditions, which will be better or worse, according to their economic living conditions, which allows or does not allow them access to consumer goods and food.

They invented, even though the child who travels, has greater leisure conditions, abstracts more, presents greater and better educational performance at school and this is the most obvious thing and not because he has access to more tangible and intangible elements, but, it begins that has conditions for a diet richer in all nutrients, vitamins and minerals that are essential for complete brain development, formation of synapses and most interestingly, during

classes, children who have economic security do not feel obliged to stay wondering what you will eat that day and even if you will have something to eat at home. This already makes it clear that whenever the teacher looks at her, her thoughts will be elsewhere, which does not mean that she suffers from attention deficit, just that she has concerns that no child at her age should have.

Instead of having a mature and sociological look at education and its group of dependents, they first pathologized education, through erudite speeches filled with neologisms and technical terms from Psychiatry, and when this idea was accepted, it was not difficult to happen, due to the terrible level of intellectual training of Basic Education teachers, the majority of whom brought, from Olympus, the miraculous cure and thus, the medicalization of education occurred which, instead of offering food, a balanced and healthy diet, gave a cocktail of drugs, with the promise of solving all their problems. And once again, the poorest, those on the line of extreme poverty were excluded from this *paradise*, that is, the solution to learning problems does not reach those who should and need it most, even when the much-vaunted solution is still a deception.

In this way, the cursed correlative cycle between extreme poverty and low learning rates perpetuates itself in an infinite *continuum*, without the slightest sign of a viable solution and with respect for the dignity of the human person.

THE CONCEPT OF POVERTY

Poverty can never be understood as a relative concept, because its link is directly linked to questions of comparison between two instances of an economic nature, in which those who have nothing or very little, in terms of enough to live with dignity, are considered as being on the list of poverty.

In this way, the concept of poverty is usually understood as the state of deprivation in which an individual finds himself, whose situation of what can be euphemistically called well-being is lower than the minimum that society is morally obliged to guarantee- him. Poverty in a society can be understood, therefore, as the aggregate of the state of deprivation of its members. However, some additional definitions are necessary. What is needed is a measure of individual well-being and the definition of the minimum morally acceptable well-being, quantified in the same unit of measurement. This is where the problem lies, because there is no consensus on what well-being is, on how to measure it, and much less on what is the minimum morally acceptable well-being (OSORIO; SOARES; SOUZA; 2011); However, it must be

recognized that the lack of access, in a dignified manner, to basic consumer goods, such as drinking water, a balanced diet, in terms of quality and quantity, would be an excellent indicator to determine the space where a dignified life and another begins, guided by the violence of extreme poverty, bordering on misery.

From this sociological perspective, poverty can be understood as a condition of real need, typically involving the needs of everyday life such as food, clothing, housing and basic health care, so dear to early childhood and indispensable to all of it, in its entirety. . The lack of economic resources, namely the lack of income or wealth (not necessarily just in monetary terms), is interpreted as the lack of access to these minimum conditions of human dignity.

Poverty can be classified as absolute or relative. Absolute poverty refers to a level that is consistent over time and across countries. An example of an absolute poverty indicator is the percentage of people with a daily calorie intake lower than the minimum necessary (approximately 2000/2500 kcalories). The World Bank defines extreme poverty as living on less than 1 US dollar per day, which would currently be equivalent to living on less than 5.80R\$/day or a monthly income of 174.00R\$/month.

What is classified here as absolute poverty is understood as extreme poverty, where the individual does not have even the minimum to meet the physiological needs that a day of life demands . Added to this is the fact that without adequate nutritional conditions, you will not be able to develop intellectually, because your developing body and brain require a range of energy that your daily intake does not supply, even in a deficient way.

Coulanges (2004) says that, since money appeared in the world, poverty has existed, because those who held monetary and land power needed someone who did not have it to provide them with services, in a fight against hunger and, consequently, , against death. Until the middle of the 20th century, this did not represent a social problem, because as there was no obligation for all children to go to school, this problem of malnutrition, caused by extreme poverty, was not highlighted by the coexistence of children in the school space. , denouncing a state of exception that marks the harsh global reality, much more exposed and striking in underdeveloped and developing countries.

THE RELATIONSHIP OF EXTREME POVERTY WITH LOW EDUCATIONAL AND SCHOOL PERFORMANCE INDEXES

It must be clarified, before anything else, that extreme poverty is not the cause of all student failure, but what it causes, directly and indirectly, without, however, being able to

separate it from the entire process of learning deficit, more or less pronounced. Nutritional deficits become responsible for the lack of formation of a chain of neurological processes, which are essential for the development of children's cognitive and intellectual capacity. Another detail is that their organic resistance is compromised, being subject to all types of infectious diseases, worms, hypovitaminosis, which culminates in deficient formations of the organoneurocerebral system. Therefore, it cannot be expected that a student who goes through such situations can demonstrate minimal learning potential, nor even that didactic-pedagogical interventions will have miraculous effects on their epistemic condition.

Extreme poverty hinders school performance and a study conducted by North American researchers, with 400 children, from families living in conditions below the poverty line, using brain scanning resources through magnetic resonance imaging, is beginning to consolidate a new variable that helps explain the phenomenon, the brain development of children in situations of poverty. A study in this direction states that gray matter develops insufficiently during a childhood full of nutritional deficiencies (SALAS, 2015).

The work shows that brain structures dedicated to critical learning processes are vulnerable to the environmental circumstances of poverty, such as stress, low stimulation and diet, the latter having the greatest impact on final results. The study authors point out that these brain development problems could explain up to 20% of the low academic performance of children with few resources.

The researchers, from the universities of Michigan, Duke and Wisconsin (USA), analyzed children's brain development using MRI scans performed during childhood and discovered that the brain's gray matter was significantly less developed in poor boys and girls. More specifically, the gray matter of the frontal lobe, temporal lobe and hippocampus was up to 10% smaller in children raised below the poverty line in the USA (SALAS, 2015).

The authors compared the information from brain MRI scans with the academic performance of these children, reaching the conclusion that the lack of gray matter development would explain between 15% and 20% of the learning deficits of students living below the poverty line. 'With these data, we demonstrate that children from low-income families show atypical structural development in several critical areas of the brain, including total gray matter, the frontal lobe, the temporal lobe, and the hippocampus' (HAIR et al *apud* SALAS, 2015, p. 3).

It begins by understanding that the child, whose parents live in conditions of extreme poverty, is already born at a serious nutritional disadvantage, because the parents, not having the economic conditions that allow them to have access to consumer goods, healthy and balanced food, mineral supplements for the pregnant mother, in order to meet vitamin and

mineral deficiencies, this individual already arrives into the world with their brain system compromised and with synaptic and physical development below what is considered ideal for full organic, cognitive and intellectual development.

These families end up without access to gynecological consultations, prenatal exams, medicines to control diseases that can affect pregnant women, medicines against anemia, folic acid, an adequate nutritional diet, safe and healthy places to rest, that is, all the training The child's brain, from the fetus onwards, is already compromised and what is reflected at school is nothing more than an expression of the social condition in which it was generated. She, in itself, cannot be penalized, because she is not to blame for being born into a family that did not have the minimum for her survival with what is needed to guarantee human dignity.

This child, at the moment he begins to develop, will need to mobilize energy and protein resources for his survival and no longer for the formation of nerve cells essential for the epistemic and gnosiological construction of his life. What we seek to demonstrate here is that in the race for survival, those who have the greatest vital energy load will stand out and when these children arrive at school, there is already a nutritional gap that has caused mild or acute mental retardation, preventing them from walking. , regarding the cognitive aspect, at the same speed as other children who did not experience similar problems.

When a child feels hungry, there is a whole set of bacteria in their stomach and intestine that need to be nourished, because they are the ones who will break down the protein chains and release energy to be absorbed into the bloodstream and supply an entire complex nutrition system. throughout the body, releasing minerals and vitamins essential to the development of organic functions. However, there is, in an unrevealed way, a struggle for survival, because like man, this bacterial flora is made up of living organisms that also fight to live. As there are no nutrients for their nutrition, they begin to devour the wall of the stomach and intestine of the host, which in this case is the human being, and this causes losses in the ability to absorb mineral nutrients in the future, which results in failed results in protein compensation. -mineral for nutritionally deficient children when they arrive at school, in terms of the epistemological response.

It is not extreme poverty that limits the epistemological development of these children, it is its impact on their living conditions, which generates a paradox, because, by combating the condition of extreme poverty, families could nourish themselves better, with this, promoting greater and better conditions for children's systematic advances in cognitive and intellectual fields.

CONCLUSION

Extreme poverty has been a serious public order problem in Brazil and with the requirement that all children be included in schools, it ended up showing a facet of reality that was already known by researchers and politicians, but which they could deny as needed. at your pleasure and in order to meet the political game.

For didactic purposes, it should be clarified that *extreme poverty* does not yet mean a state of misery, according to the classification mechanisms defined by the World Bank. What is recommended to be defined is that, in addition to not eating correctly and necessary for good organic development, these children, coming from families in such conditions, live in unsanitary conditions, lacking treated water, basic sanitation, sewage and personal hygiene.

There is also a psychological issue linked to this, that such children are scared, irritable, fearful, shy and this is due to the fact that they are hungry, which highlights a primitive feeling that accompanies human beings, especially children and women [*most notably, the first*] since ages very distant from contemporary times, but the practice still survives in several parts of the world: the act of cannibalism. This is a phylogenetic feeling that accompanies the species as an amalgam.

The hungry child lives with the fear that he will be devoured by his parents or other adults in extreme conditions like him and, for this reason, he behaves resisting everything and, at night, he does not sleep, firstly because of the stomach pain. It bothers her to extremes, then because in the few breaks she sleeps she dreams about food and, finally, because she fears being attacked while she sleeps by a hungry adult.

a curriculum that allows the construction of a critical individual continues . Actions must be taken to implement public policies that put an end [*at least*] to extreme poverty and misery.

This essay discussed the fact that this social condition inevitably leads to low levels of school performance, due to hunger, lack of basic care, hygiene, malnutrition, coexistence and contact with open sewage situations, which come to generating worms of all species, leading children to very precarious conditions of life and social development, impacting their ability to progress at school.

School lunch programs were created with the aim of combating malnutrition among children from needy families; However, this appears to be much more of a euphemism and cannot eliminate the problem, because a child's nutritional deficiencies are not concentrated in a single time of day, much less in a single meal per day.

Thinking about the condition for resolving the issue of hunger as a way of minimizing impacts on educational-school learning involves the development of efficient public policies that prove to be effective, seeking long-term perspectives, paying attention to the direct and indirect results that are expected to be achieved and that are demonstrated, through studies and scientific confirmation.

What is proposed is the political-social confrontation of this evil that plagues the 21st Century and with this, there is the expectation that the levels of knowledge and intellectuality will tend to rise, firstly because they will not have to worry about whether they will have what to eat and if, at least they will eat at the end of the day and on weekends and during school holidays and after that there will be no disputes over nutrients that conflict with their respective conditions of physical and mental growth.

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